

Medicinal Plants used in Bangladeshi Perspective for Body Weight Loss

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Abstract

Background: One of the major illnesses that causes more than twenty-five million deaths globally each year is obesity. Synthetic medications for weight loss are not very effective and have a lot of adverse effects. The use of herbs in managing obesity has gained interest in recent years.

Methods: An observation about different herbal preparations used in Bangladesh has been done. Data have been collected from different reputed Bangladeshi journals and literature site. The effectiveness, safety and different use of herbal weight management in Bangladesh are gathered in this study. A summary of popular herbal medicines, like green tea, garcinia, and ginger, and their possible advantages in aiding in weight loss are also included in this study.

Results: It was found that most people in Bangladesh use green tea as anti-obesity treatment, while vinegar is also a good option for them. This study provide a brief notes of the plant sources which are available in Bangladesh to serve as synthetic and semi-synthetic anti-obesity drugs.

Conclusion: The use of herbal weight therapy as a holistic and all-natural method of managing weight has grown in popularity. Continued research is likely needed to ascertain the efficacy and safety of pharmaceutically active compounds that may have the ability to cause weight loss, as well as medicinal plants and herbal extracts.

Keywords: Medicinal plant; weight loss; green tea; anti-obesity; orlistat

1. Introduction: Obesity is the result of the body's ill or unfavorable response to excess fat accumulation. The body mass index (BMI), which is a weight-for-height indicator, is frequently used to categorize persons as overweight or obese. Medications such as sibutramine and orlistat are used to treat obesity and overweight. Not only are these medications expensive, but they also have negative effects and are not very effective at treating obesity. Obesity may harm children, although the majority of treatments for obese children have produced results with very little impact, indicating the need for more targeted, concentrated research.

An imbalance between calories used and calories consumed leads to obesity and overweight. Two factors have contributed to overweight and obesity worldwide: 1) A greater consumption of foods high in fat, salt, and sugar but low in vitamins, minerals, and other micronutrients; 2) A decline in physical activity brought on by a shift in transportation patterns, an increase in urbanization, and the sedentary nature of many occupations [1, 2]. Globally, obesity and overweight are associated with a higher death toll than underweight. For instance, in nations where obesity and overweight are more common than underweight, 70% of the world's population resides. It is acknowledged that the most important risk factor for type 2 diabetes is obesity. Increased blood plasma concentrations of free fatty acid (FFA) are linked to obesity, specifically intraabdominal adiposity. This has a detrimental impact on insulin sensitivity in both the liver and muscle. Type 2 diabetes is predisposed to develop in addition to insulin resistance due to less insulin production. It is possible for both lipo-toxicity and glucotoxicity to start and facilitate a vicious cycle that is responsible for the metabolic impairment. Years of poor glucose tolerance precede the late onset of diabetes in obese individuals. The incapacity of the pancreatic Langerhans B cells to sustain their high rate of insulin release in response to glucose is a sign of diabetes development [3].

With potential advantages over conventional weight loss techniques in terms of safety, tolerability, and long-term efficacy, herbal weight loss therapy has grown in popularity. The idea of herbal weight loss therapy will be discussed in this article, along with some well-known herbs, their alleged modes of action, and the research that backs their application. Herbal weight loss therapy uses preparations and remedies derived from plants to help in weight loss. It is based on the characteristics of several herbs, which have long been utilized for their possible effects on energy expenditure, appetite control, metabolism, and fat breakdown. These herbs are frequently offered as tinctures, teas, supplements, or as a component of a healthy diet and way of life [4, 5]. Bangladesh is a subtropical nation with an abundance of naturally occurring medicinal plants. Even in the early 1980s, the nation's herbal medicine companies—both Unani and Ayurvedic—were sourcing 80% of their supplies from the nation's natural forests, with the remaining 20% coming from imports [6]. Dietary phytochemicals have recently aroused considerable interest as the potential therapeutic agents for health promotion and to counteract obesity [7]. Although the traditional medical system has been used for a long time to treat a variety of illnesses and conditions, there are no documented safety or effectiveness studies [8].

The *Camellia sinensis* plant's leaves are used to make green tea extract. It contains a lot of polyphenols, especially catechins, which are thought to have fat-burning and thermogenic qualities. Green tea extract may boost energy expenditure, fat oxidation, and metabolism,

according to research. Its antioxidant qualities may also improve general health and wellbeing, which is why many people include it in weight loss plans. Tropical fruit *garcinia cambogia* is frequently found in diet pills. Its active ingredient, hydroxy-citric acid (HCA), is thought to prevent the fat-storing enzyme citrate lyase from working. According to certain research, HCA may reduce appetite and prevent the body from turning too many carbohydrates into fat. Nevertheless, additional investigation is required to determine its long-term effectiveness and safety [9]. The efficaciousness of medicinal herbal supplements in the management of numerous chronic ailments has led to their widespread use. Compared to many chemically synthesized drugs, they are less expensive and have fewer or no harmful side effects [10]. Economical substitutes for the treatment of obesity may be made available through the development of standardized, secure, and efficient medications derived from plants. Consequently, it is imperative to generate and evaluate an extensive array of plant extracts, and this methodology may serve as a catalyst for the identification of anti-obesity medications derived from medicinal plants. The purpose of this study is to present a concise overview of the plant sources that can be used to make synthetic and semi-synthetic anti-obesity medications in Bangladesh.

2. Methodology: Data have been collected from different reputed international journals, website and literature. All data were analyzed by checking their prevalence and compliance with medicinal plants uses in Bangladesh. The following were the main search terms: botanical remedy, natural, alternative, phytonutrients, phytochemicals, efficacy, safety, anti-obesity, obesity, weight loss, BMI, plant extracts, herbal supplements and herbal medicines.

3. Results: Natural anti-obesity supplements have the ability to reduce body weight through a variety of methods, and their effects can be categorized.

Table 1: Functions of anti-obesity medicinal plants and preparations

Functions	Anti-obesity preparation	Mechanism
Lowering the rate of lipid absorption	Green tea, herbal tea, chitosan	Preventing the action of pancreatic lipase
Stopping adipogenesis	Capsicum, garlic, flaxseed, turmeric,	Preventing the differentiation of adipocytes
Reducing food intake	Aloe-vera, Pomegranate leaf, cucumber, salad	Suppressing hunger and consuming less food

Some bioactive metabolites can boost energy expenditure and postprandial carbohydrate oxidation by raising the basic metabolic rate, which intensifies thermogenesis. This happens when the sympathetic nervous system is stimulated, activating the β_1 -, β_2 -, and β_3 -adrenoreceptors [11]. This function may be carried out through influencing the expression of metabolic genes, activating the AMPK pathway in 3T3-L1 preadipocytes, and causing the expression of uncoupling proteins (UCP1, 2, or 3). Consequently, these processes will help the body in burning more calories and extra fat [12, 13]. By altering gut hormones and secreting the proteins involved in appetite sensation, such as cholecystokinin (CCK), anti-obesity plants,

like those that contain alkaloids and glycol-steroids, can suppress appetite and induce satiety (much like the synthetic agent sibutramine), which helps in appetite control.

Table 2: List of herbs most commonly used in Bangladesh

Scientific name	Local name	Plant part used
<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Green tea	Leaves
<i>Aloe vera</i>	Kumari	Leaves/ whole plant
<i>Emblica officinalis</i>	amloki	Fruit
<i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i>	Methi	Seeds
<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Haldi	Rhizome
<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Ada	Rhizome
<i>Allium sativum</i>	Rason	Stem bulb & roots

Those plants listed in (table - 2) are most commonly used in Bangladesh to reduce fats and weight. Some of them used as spice or medicine in food sample and preparations. There are some herbal preparations available in Bangladeshi market, that are occasionally consumed by general public but sometimes they use those medicines without proper prescription and consultation.

Table 3: Some common anti-obesity herbal drugs in Bangladeshi market with dosage form

Serial no.	Name of preparation	Dosage form
1	Orlistat	Capsule
2	Krishocap	Capsule
3	Spirulina	Capsule
4	Green tea	Beverage, tablet, capsule
5	Apple cider vinegar	Beverage

Most medicinal plants have unclear mechanisms of action against obesity. However, various explanations for these plants have been put forth, including decreased pre-adipocyte differentiation and proliferation, increased energy expenditure, decreased lipid absorption, decreased energy intake, or increased lipolysis and low lipogenesis. Green tea and Oolong tea inhibit pancreatic lipase, which results in decreased energy intake. Weight loss is a result of the inhibitory action of polyphenols found in tea extracts, such as epicatechin-3-gallate, L-epicatechin, and epigallocatechin, against pancreatic lipase [14]. Different dosage form of herbal medicine used to reduce weight, listed in (table - 3) those are most common in terms of use in Bangladesh.

Figure 1: Trend & scenario of in what percent anti-obesity medicine are used

(Figure 1) represents the frequency of usage of these medicine those are available in Bangladeshi market. These drugs are easily available in market and can be purchased without prescription. There is a paucity of published data, a lack of clinical trials, or a low quality of evidence for many herbal weight loss products in perspective of Bangladesh. Herbal products for weight reduction may be effective in the management of obesity and associated disorders. Consistent and safe herbal product for weight reduction is a need of developed and developing countries.

4. Discussion: Multiple research investigations have demonstrated the ability of a range of natural food ingredients and medicinal plant preparations to increase satiety, speed up weight loss, and increase metabolism [15 – 18]. These powerful plants' ability to reduce weight may be attributed to their fiber content, which reduces appetite, or—more likely—to particular phytochemicals like caffeine, phenolic compounds, and other active ingredients that have the ability to down-regulate obesity by increasing thermogenesis, decreasing lipogenesis, enhancing lipolysis, and reducing lipid absorption [19]. Evidences are emerging to support that an increasing consumption of herbs are effective strategy for obesity control and weight management. Utilizing plants and plant-based products may help control the rising incidence of metabolic syndrome. There aren't many medications available to treat or prevent obesity, but it still need to think about their side effects, effectiveness, and cost. People have been using natural products as plant-based dietary supplements to control their weight for centuries, all over the world [20, 21].

It is commonly known that using natural substitutes can help reduce obesity, bodily infection and extend life expectancy [22], and they are good choice for ideal nutrition value [23]. While some plants in Bangladesh have the potential to combat obesity, local researchers have not given them much attention, and others are not even encouraged. More research in this field

with carefully planned clinical trials focused on both safety and efficacy with these plants materials is needed in order to obtain the additional anti-obesity data about those plants that are needed. Herbal medicine is in high demand and continues to grow worldwide. Unfortunately, there haven't been many trials or experiments in this field until recently, which is indicative of our ignorance of the natural world. Though there are many medicinal plants in the world, only about one-third of them have been found and identified as having therapeutic value. To assess and guarantee the efficacy and safety of medicinal plants, as well as their possible metabolites in the treatment of inflammatory diseases and ulcers, more thorough and trustworthy scientific research is still required. To ensure both reproducibility and uniformity of the active components, the quality of the targeted active compounds should be tested frequently or batch-to-batch.

5. Conclusion: Herbal weight loss therapy presents a healthy method of managing weight and may offer extra assistance to individuals pursuing weight loss in a healthful manner. But it's important to keep in mind that herbal remedies aren't miracle cures. They ought to be combined with a healthy diet, consistent exercise, and way of life adjustments. There are several plants described in Ayurveda for weight management. But so far, no systematic and well-designed screening is attempted to come up with an effective herbal weight loss product. Ideally, medicinal plants should demonstrate improvements in biomarkers such as glycemia, lipids, and blood pressure, should be aware of the action's mechanism. Shouldn't have serious detrimental effects of any kind. Before those potential alternative medications can be suggested for the long-term management of obesity, comprehensive clinical and observational studies for their long-term safety and effectiveness should be carried out.

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